

Prognostic Factors Associated with Survival in Breast Cancer After Curative-Intent Radiotherapy

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Prognostic factors affecting mortality after external radiotherapy (RT) in breast cancer (BC) patients are still open to research. This study aims to evaluate survival factors with regional data in patients with BC who received curative-intent RT.

Methods: A single-center retrospective observational study was conducted at the Department of Radiation Oncology in a university hospital. Patients aged 18 years or older, who did not have metastasis and received RT, were included in the study. For the analysis of patient survival data, the Kaplan-Meier method was used, and the comparison of survival times based on categorizable parameters was performed using the Log-rank analysis.

Results: A total of 51 patients were included in the study. The overall survival and disease-specific survival times are 78.2+ months. The overall survival time decreased statistically significantly with the progression of T stage ($p=0.038$). Patients who did not develop metastases had substantially longer survival compared to those who did ($p<0.001$). A statistically significant difference was found in the overall survival rates of patients based on their remission and recurrence status ($p<0.001$).

Conclusion: T stage, presence of metastasis, and hormone therapy are the main factors affecting survival.

KEYWORDS: Breast Cancer, Curative, Radiotherapy, Prognosis

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INTRODUCTION

Multidisciplinary guidelines have been updated in recent years to standardize management of breast cancer (BC) controversies related to personal and tumor characteristics as a result of being a diverse group of tumors with a broad range of morphologically and molecularly distinct subtypes, each of which causes different biological behaviors, presentations, and prognoses [1, 2].

Complex BC therapy continues to include radiation therapy (RT), which is now based on the patient's risk status and tailored RT approaches, considering patient input [3]. To provide personalized suggestions, it is now essential to understand the factors that affect survival [4, 5].

Various well-defined factors can increase the risk of breast cancer. These include: family history, nulliparity, early

menarche, late menopause, obesity in postmenopausal women, high endogenous estradiol levels, advanced age, and a personal history of in situ or invasive breast cancer. While reducing the risk of having children, early first birth age, and an increased number of births and breastfeeding likely have a protective effect. Both oral contraceptives and hormone replacement therapies carry a small but increased risk. Alcohol consumption increases risk, while physical activity is expected to be protective [6, 7]. Lymph node status and tumor size are the most important prognostic factors for breast cancer recurrence and overall survival [8]. Other predictive factors include tumor grade, lymphatic and vascular invasion, the Ki-67 proliferation marker, the patient's age at diagnosis, estrogen and progesterone receptor status, HER-2/neu status, uPA, PAI-1, and genetic profile [9,

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10]. In light of all this information, we therefore aimed to evaluate survival factors with regional data in patients with BC who received curative-intent radiotherapy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This single-center retrospective observational study was conducted in the department of radiation oncology of a university hospital between 2006 and 2007. It was approved by the Faculty of Medicine Ethics Committee before the study, with decision number 11 dated 02.05.2013.

Patients aged 18 years or older, who received curative intent (CI) RT, that is, patients who did not have metastasis and received RT with an adjuvant (after surgery and chemotherapy) radiotherapy indication, were included in the study. Patients who were metastatic at the time of diagnosis and whose data could not be accessed were excluded from the study. Patient data was obtained from the main science department records through file scanning. Attempts were made to obtain patients' missing information by calling them

individually and through the hospital information system. The demographic characteristics of the patients (gender, age groups, place of application, place of residence), medical histories (number of pregnancies, number of births, menopausal status, family history, presenting complaint, side of the disease), pathology report information (tumor pathology, presence of widespread DCIS, histological grade, nuclear grade, lymphovascular invasion, perineural invasion, tumor diameter, number of lymph nodes removed and positive, surgical margin, invasion of peritumoral adipose tissue, peritumoral lymphocytic infiltration, p53, estrogen receptor status, progesterone receptor status, Cerb b2), types of surgery performed, and information on chemotherapy (CT), hormone therapy (HT), and radiotherapy (RT) received were extracted. A graphical summary describing the general stages of the study is shown in Figure 1. Another graphical summary summarizing all stages of this study is also shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Graphical Abstract of Study

Figure 1. General Graphical Summary of The Study

Statistical analyses

For categorical data, the number and frequency of occurrences in each category (n, %) were used for presentation. For numerical data, the mean, standard deviation, or median, along with 95% confidence intervals, were used for presentation. Cross-tabulation statistics were used in statistical comparisons made with descriptive data. For the analysis of patient survival data, the Kaplan-Meier method was used, and the comparison of survival times based on categorizable parameters was performed using the Log-rank analysis. For the graphical representation of the data, pie charts were used for descriptive data, and Kaplan-Meier survival curves were used for survival data. All statistical analyses in the study were conducted using SPSS v15.0 software, and a p-value of <0.05 was accepted as the statistical significance limit for all analyses.

RESULTS

A total of 51 patients were included in the study. Fifty of the patients included in the study were female, and one was male. The average age of the entire group was 50.5 ± 10.5 years. The frequency of cases was highest among those aged 40-60 (n=33, 64.7%). Forty (78.4%) of the patients lived in the city center. The percentage of those with three or more pregnancies was 52.9%. When examining the menopausal

status of patients at the time of diagnosis, it was found that the largest group of patients was in the postmenopausal category (n=25, 49%). It was observed that patients most frequently presented with a breast mass (64.7%). During the follow-up of the study patients, distant metastasis developed in 13 patients (25.5%). The most common sites for metastasis development were the brain, lungs, and bones. Table 1 and 2 shows the surgical outcomes for the patients. The most frequently performed modified radical mastectomy + axillary dissection was (n=39, 76.5%). In the pathological evaluation of surgically removed tissues, invasive ductal carcinoma was found to be the most common (n= 38, 74.5%). The most common histological grade was 2 (n = 28, 54.9%), and the most common nuclear grade was also 2 (n = 27, 52.9%). The frequencies of lymphovascular and perineural invasion in patients were 62.7% (n=32) and 15.7% (n=8), respectively. The extracted mass sizes were most commonly between 2 and 5 cm (n = 34, 66.7%). The predominant T stage in patients was T2 (n=32), accounting for 62.7%, and the N stage was N2 (n=21), accounting for 41.2%. The majority of patients were in the Stage 3A (n=24, 4.1%) group. The group with the highest number of metastatic lymph nodes was in the 4-9 range (n=21, 41.2%). 56.9% of patients were estrogen receptor negative (n=29), 27.5% were progesterone receptor negative (n=14), and 54.9% were HER-2 negative (28%).

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When evaluating the patients' chemotherapy treatments, it was found that the number of patients who had not received chemotherapy before surgery and after ERT was high ($n = 42$, 92.2%; $n = 49$, 96.1%, respectively). Information on chemotherapy and hormone therapy is presented in Table 3.

When evaluating the radiotherapy information of the patients, it was observed that 41.2% of them received treatment to the $gd+scf+axilla$ region ($n=21$), the most frequently used number of fractions was 25 (80.4%), and the total dose was 5000 cGy (78.4%). The patients' radiotherapy information summaries are presented in Table 4.

Table 5 examines the analysis of the variables on survival. The overall survival and disease-specific survival times are 78.2+ months. The lowest survival rate was in the 60+ age group, with a survival rate of 70.8+ months. It was observed that there was no statistically significant difference in overall survival times based on age, menopausal status, family history, pregnancy status, and childbirth status. It was observed that overall survival time decreased statistically significantly with the progression of T stage ($p=0.038$). No statistically significant difference was found in overall survival based on nerve status, estrogen receptor, progesterone receptor, and HER2neu positivity. There was no statistically significant difference found in overall survival estimates based on hormone therapy status, but clinically, survival was 14 months longer in those receiving hormone therapy. There was a statistically significant difference in overall survival between patients who developed metastases and those who did not, with the latter having significantly longer survival ($p<0.001$). A statistically significant difference was found in the overall survival rates of patients based on their remission and recurrence status ($p<0.001$).

DISCUSSION

In a large center in the Eastern Anatolia region of Türkiye, T stage and presence of metastasis were identified as two variables affecting survival in breast cancer patients after curative-intent radiotherapy (Table 5). Subtype, grade, lymph node status, and stage of illness are some of the variables that impact breast cancer treatment and prognosis. The significance of aggressively seeking prognostic criteria is shown by the fact that patients with identical prognostic features might have different clinical outcomes [11]. Our findings may have been caused by a process where the size of cancer stem cells dictates their migratory and proliferative capabilities. This cell type's capacity to migrate and proliferate grows in tandem with tumor size [12].

Distant metastases are still the primary cause of death in breast cancer, even after curative-intent radiation, according to the literature [13]. We conclude that intrinsic tumor characteristics broadly impact the outcome of metastatic patients regardless of whether they receive curative-intent radiation [14].

Cancer is not caused by menopause per se, although a woman's risk of developing the disease increases as she ages.

Despite the impact of various biological factors that dictate the breast cancer prognosis in premenopausal women, our investigation did not find any mortality in this group [15]. This is in addition to the fact that premenopausal BC patients and postmenopausal BC patients may have different causes, risk factors, and therapeutic approaches [16].

LIMITATIONS

This study presents several limitations. First, it was a single-center, low-volume study. This can create a sample size bias that limits the generalizability of the study results. Although sample size bias can threaten the extrapolation of the results, our study population is representative of the target population, allowing us to focus on the clinical significance. Beyond this, due to the nature of the analyses performed on a disease group with a long survival time, the effects of many parameters on survival could not be clearly evaluated since the median mortality was not reached in the case group during follow-up. This might result in survivor bias.

CONCLUSION

T stage, presence of metastasis, and hormone therapy are the main factors affecting survival. Formulating individual recommendations can be the merit of future studies, depending on the prognostic factors.

Author Contributions

The authors confirm their contributions to the article as follows: Study conception and design: Ozlem Eser Kilinc and Orhan Sezen. Data collection: Ozlem Eser Kilinc. Analysis and interpretation of results: Orhan Sezen, Hilal Tahirler, and Yilmaz Sahin. Preparation of the draft article: Ozlem Eser Kilinc and Orhan Sezen. All authors reviewed the results and approved the final version of the article.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors approved that they have no conflict of interest.

Ethical Approval

It was approved by the Faculty of Medicine Ethics Committee before the study, with decision number 11 dated 02.05.2013. All participants provided written informed consent in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Data Availability

The data used to support the findings of this study are included within the article

Data sharing statement

None

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Table 1. Clinical and pathological characteristics of the patients

Variables		n, %
Type of surgery	MRM+ Axillary dissection	39 (76.5)
	BCS+ Axillary dissection	8 (15.7)
	MRM	2 (3.9)
	BCS	1 (2)
	Simple mastectomy +LND	1 (2)
Result of pathology	Invasive ductal carcinoma	38 (74.5)
	Invasive ductal carcinoma+ Invasive lobular carcinoma	4 (7.8)
	Invasive lobular carcinoma	3 (5.9)

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	Medullary carcinoma	2 (3.9)
	Papillary carcinoma	2 (3.9)
	Lobular carcinoma in situ	1(2)
	Mucinous carcinoma	1 (2)
Presence of disseminated DCIS	Presence	21 (41.2)
	Absence	13 (25.5)
	Unknown	17 (33.3)
Histological grade	Grade 1	12
	Grade 2	2854.9
	Grade 3	917.6
	Unknown	1325.5
Nuclear grade	Grade 2	27 (52.9)
	Grade 3	10 (19.6)
	Unknown	14 (27.5)
Lymphovascular invasion	Presence	32 (62.7)
	Absence	8 (15.7)
	Unknown	11 (21.6)
Perineural invasion	Presence	8 (15.7)
	Absence	5 (9.8)
	Unknown	38 (74.5)
Surgical margin status	Negative	15 (29.4)
	Pozitive	7 (13.7)
	Unknown	29 (56.9)

MRM: modified radical mastectomy; BCS: breast-conserving surgery; LND: lymph node dissection; DCIS: dictal carcinoma in situ

Table 2. Clinical and pathological characteristics of the patients

Variables		n, %
T stage	T1	7 (13.7)
	T2	32 (62.7)
	T3	10 (19.6)
	T4	2 (3.9)
N stage	N1	14 (27.5)
	N2	21 (41.2)
	N3	2 (3.9)
	N0	14 (27.5)
Disease stage	Stage 1	2 (3.9)
	Stage 2A	12 (23.5)
	Stage 2B	9 (17.6)
	Stage 3A	24 (47.1)
	Stage 3B	2 (3.9)
	Stage 3C	2 (3.9)
Number of lymph nodes removed	0-9	12 (23.5)
	10-19	35 (68.6)
	≥20	4 (7.8)
Number of metastatic lymph nodes	0	14 (27.5)
	1	9 (17.6)
	2	2 (3.9)

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	3	3 (5.9)
	4-9	21 (41.2)
	10-15	1 (2)
	≥16	1 (2)
ER positivity	Absent	29 (56.9)
	0-20	4 (7.8)
	20-50	3 (5.9)
	50-80	3 (5.9)
	80-100	8 (15.7)
	Unknown	4 (7.8)
PR positivity	Absent	14 (27.5)
	0-20	10 (19.6)
	20-50	5 (9.8)
	50-80	4 (7.8)
	80-100	14 (27.5)
	Unknown	4 (7.8)
Her2neu positivity	Negative	28 (54.9)
	1+	3 (5.9)
	2+	2 (3.9)
	3+	13 (25.5)
	Unknown	5 (9.8)

Table 3. Characteristics of chemotherapy and Hormone Therapy of Patients

Variables		N,%	
CT before surgery	Absent	47 (92.2)	
	3 cycles	2	3.9
	4 cycles	1	2.0
	6 cycles	1	2.0
CT before ERT	Yok	1	2.0
	3 cycles	2	3.9
	4 cycles	13	25.5
	6 cycles	21	41.2
	8 cycles	14	27.5
Type of CT before ERT	Adriamycin + cyclophosphamide + docetaxel	10	19.6
	FeC	9	17.6
	Cyclophosphamide + epirubicin	8	15.7
	Adriablastin + Endoxan + Taxotere	6	11.8
	FAC	4	7.8
	Adriablastin + Endoxan	3	5.9
	Epirubicin + cyclophosphamide	2	3.9
	Adriamycin + Endoxan + 5-FU	2	3.9
	Docetaxel + doxorubicin + cyclophosphamide	1	2.0
	MTX + Endoxan + 5-FU Adriamycin + Cyclophosphamide	1	2.0
	Adriamycin + cyclophosphamide + docetaxel	1	2.0
	Absent	1	2.0
	Unknown	3	5.9
CT after ERT	Absent	49	96.1
	2 cycles	1	2.0
	9 cycles	1	2.0
Hormone therapy	Absent	14	27.5
	Present	35	68.6
	Unknown	2	3.9
Type of hormone therapy	Tamoxifen	17	33.3

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	Anastrozole	8	15.7
	Letrozole	8	15.7
	Absent	18	35.3

CT: chemotherapy; ERT: external radiotherapy; FEC: Fluorouracil, Adriamycin, and Cytosin;

FeC: fluorouracil, epirubicin hydrochloride, and cyclophosphamide; FU: fluorouracil; MTX: methotrexate

Table 4. Characteristics of external radiotherapy of patients

Variables	N,%		
ERT area	Gd+scf+axillary	21	41.2
	Gd	12	23.5
	Gd+scf	6	11.8
	Gd+scf+aksilla+mi	6	11.8
	Meme+scf+aksilla	4	7.8
	Meme	2	3.9
Number of ERT fractions	25	41	80.4
	30	8	15.7
	24	1	2.0
	5	1	2.0
Total amount of ERT	5000cGy	40	78.4
	6000cGy	9	17.6
	1000cGy	1	2.0
	5520cGy	1	2.0

ERT: external radiotherapy; Gd:.....; scf:.....; mi:

Table 5. Effect of variables on survival

	Mean	Standart error	%95 interval (Min-Max)	Confidence	Median	Standart error	%95 interval (Min-Max)	Confidence
Age								
<40	77.875	3.859	70.312	85.438
40-49					83.000	2.315	78.463	87.537
50-59	81.000	3.402	74.333	87.667
≥60	70.806	6.335	58.389	83.222
Menapous								
Premenopausal	No mortality							
Perimenopausal					83.000	2.211	78.666	87.334
Postmenopausal	79.054	2.749	73.666	84.442
Family History								
Absent	83.863		2.971		78.040		89.686	
Present	74.917		4.969		65.178		84.655	
Number of pregnancies								
0	70.000	10.765	48.901	91.099
2	72.800	3.757	65.437	80.163
≥3					83.000	2.182	78.723	87.277
Birth rate								
0	70.000	10.765	48.901	91.099

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2					83.000	.000	.	.
≥3	78.808	2.931	73.063	84.554
Unknown					73.000	39.082	.000	149.601
T stage								
T1	No mortality							
T2	81.060	2.334	76.486	85.634	83.000			
T3	65.889	9.120	48.014	83.764	.			
T4	47.000	16.971	13.738	80.262	23.000			
N stage								
N0	75.587	4.411	66.941	84.234
N1	79.923	2.337	75.343	84.503	83.000	2.325	78.442	87.558
N2	76.800	5.148	66.711	86.889
N3	No mortality							
ERT								
Absent	76.361		3.771		68.970		83.753	
Present	83.219		3.075		77.191		89.246	
PR								
Absent	71.949		6.230		59.738		84.160	
Present	82.469		2.579		77.415		87.523	
Her2/neu								
Absent	80.209		2.302		75.697		84.721	
Present	76.688		5.941		65.043		88.332	
Presence of metastases								
Absent	85.000	.816	83.400	86.600
Present	64.067	6.875	50.593	77.541	80.000	16.415	47.826	112.174
Remission-recurrence								
Remission	85.000	.816	83.400	86.600
metastases	70.625	6.266	58.344	82.906	80.000	22.947	35.025	124.975
Recurrence and metastases	28.000	9.000	10.360	45.640	19.000	.	.	.

ER: external radiotherapy; PR: progesterone